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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: June 2014

Katie Frey

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Visual Astronomy Display for June 2014

Highlights...

- **Jupiter's Great Red Spot is shrinking?** Images show how the largest storm in the solar system has changed over time;
- A sequence of short videos detailing five different **methods for detecting extrasolar planets**;
- Our sun is constantly surprising us. In addition solar flares, this weeks playlist includes a video about a **square shaped hole in the sun**;
- Mars orbiters have discovered **new craters on the surface of Mars** formed after recent impacts;
- A simulation of **Venus Express preforming an atmosphere-skimming maneuver** to gather more data about this shrouded planet;
- A animation of **the orbits of all known exoplanets** of single stars; and
- A description of **the landmark observations of BICEP2** that provided the first direct evidence of the Big Bang.

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Katie Frey

Assistant Head Librarian at [Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian](#)

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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CfA Bibliography for June 2014

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